
MEMORANDUM

TO: The Honourable Chairman and Members, Committee on Legal, Constitutional, and Parliamentary Affairs - Parliament of Ghana

FROM: Alliance for Equality and Diversity (AfED)

SUBJECT: The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021: Impact Analysis and Recommendations

DATE: 28 September 2021

CC: Office of the President and Attorney General and Ministry of Justice

1. We respectfully submit this Memorandum in response to the request for written Memoranda in respect of the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021*.
2. We are a coalition of 13 organisations with members and representation all across the 16 regions of Ghana. Our alliance aims to ensure the protection of the human rights of all persons, especially sexual and gender minorities (Lesbians, Gays, Bisexuals, Transgenders, Intersex, Queer and others (LGBTIQ)).
3. The enactment of this Bill into law will adversely affect our constituents. In this regard, we have held broad consultations with our members across the country and have developed this Memorandum with insights from these engagements for your consideration.
4. Firstly, the Memorandum gives a contextual introduction of the issues about the situation of LGBTIQ persons in Ghana and reactions to the bill from across the world. It is followed by an analysis of the basis or reasoning for the proposal of the Bill. An impact analysis where five (5) main negative impacts of the bill is included, amongst many. We follow this with recommendations and a conclusion which proposes the possible best way forward.
5. We remain available to provide further information as you may require and to appear before you to give an oral presentation of our Memorandum at any public hearing or your request as the Committee.

Introduction/Context

Ghana's Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Bill, 2021¹ has been described as an extreme Bill as it stretches beyond criminalising LGBTIQ persons.² If enacted into law, it will violate the human rights of not only LGBTIQ persons, for whom it is meant but also a more significant number of people, organisations and individuals.

Ghana's proposed Bill departs from progress experienced from other African countries that have decriminalised same-sex sexual relations and have gone further to enact laws that protect LGBTIQ persons against violence, discrimination and human rights abuse. Mozambique, in 2015, removed same-sex sexual relations and activities as a crime from their laws³. Mozambique is also following the likes of neighbouring South Africa, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Ivory Coast and others, where adult consensual same-sex conduct is not a crime.⁴ Parliamentarians in Angola voted in 2019 to remove the so-called "vices against nature" provision in their criminal laws, in effect, decriminalizing all same-sex conduct and established a new penal code that will prohibit discrimination.⁵

Ghana already has in its criminal offences Act 1960 (Act 29) the criminalization of unnatural carnal knowledge, which is a colonial legacy inherited from the British like all other British former colonies in Africa. Section 104(1)(b) of the Criminal Offences Act, which is purported to criminalise consensual same-sex activities, is unclear and vague. Human Rights Watch has identified that this law has contributed to human rights abuse, violence and discrimination against LGBTIQ persons in Ghana.⁶ The Bill, therefore, provides an opportunity for lawmakers to make the criminalisation of LGBTIQ persons more explicit and clearer, which will also further entrench the already existing abuse and violence LGBTIQ persons face.

Various international organisations have described the Bill as dangerous for democratic tenure and against Ghana's international human rights obligations. Amnesty International believes that the Bill stirs up hatred, persecution and discrimination against the LGBTIQ community in Ghana.⁷ They have argued that the Bill goes against various provisions of Ghana's constitution and international human rights treaties to which Ghana is a state party. Human Rights Watch

¹ The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values, Bill 2021

² Human Rights Watch 'Ghana: LGBT Activists Face Hardships After Detention; Extreme Anti-LGBT Bill Stokes Hostility' (20 September 2021) <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/09/20/ghana-lgbt-activists-face-hardships-after-detention> (accessed 21 September 2021).

³ BBC News 'Mozambique decriminalises Gay and Lesbian relationships' (1 July 2015) <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-33342963>

⁴ As above.

⁵ UN News 'UN welcomes Angola's repeal of anti-gay law, and ban on discrimination based on sexual orientation' (25 January 2021) <https://news.un.org/en/story/2019/01/1031292> (accessed 20 September 2021).

⁶ Human Rights Watch "'No Choice but to Deny Who I Am' ; Violence and Discrimination against LGBT People in Ghana' (18 January 2018) <https://www.hrw.org/report/2018/01/08/no-choice-deny-who-i-am/violence-and-discrimination-against-lgbt-people-ghana> (accessed 21 September 2021).

⁷ AfricaNews 'UN Human Rights Council opposes Ghana's anti-gay bill' (13 August 2021) <https://www.africanews.com/2021/08/13/un-human-rights-council-opposes-ghana-s-anti-gay-bill/> (accessed 28 September 2021).

has identified that the bill has a narrow understanding of human sexuality. It is discriminatory and affects individuals who express support for LGBTIQ persons.⁸

The Eminent group of United Nations Experts, Working Groups and Rapporteurs, have written a letter to the President of Ghana, His Excellency Nana Akufo-Addo, to draw his attention to how various provisions in the Bill describes a system of State-sponsored discrimination and violence of such magnitude that its adoption, in its current or in any partial form, would appear to constitute an immediate and fundamental breach of the State's obligations under international human rights law.⁹ UNAIDS has joined the call by the UN group of eminent persons to condemn the Bill and also called for its rejection. It has also warned that the legislation would be a grave setback for the HIV response in driving vulnerable people further away from essential HIV treatment, care and prevention services.

LGBTIQ persons in Ghana already face violence and human rights abuse for their imputed or real sexual orientation and gender identity. When LGBTIQ persons face violence or human rights abuse, they seldom report their issues to the police because of fear of persecution by the police.¹⁰ Many issues of violence, discrimination, and human rights abuses against LGBTIQ persons go unresolved, further fuelling the perpetuation of abuse against LGBTIQ persons with impunity.

The basis for the proposal of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021

In accordance with the 1992 Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, all bills that go before parliament must include an “explanatory memorandum” specifically detailing the “policy and principles of the bill, the defects of the existing law, the remedies proposed to deal with those, and the necessity for its introduction.” This memorandum serves as the chief subject matter for subsequent cabinet and committee discussions.¹¹ This Bill has a 16 paged Memorandum which states why this Bill needs to be passed into law. It also states incidents and laws (local and international) that support the need for a law that criminalises LGBTIQ persons and persons who seek to support LGBTIQ persons.

LGBTIQ is not Western

First, it moots the idea that LGBTIQ rights is a Western ideal being advanced in Ghana by foreign missions and diplomats. In the second paragraph of the bill, they mention the opening ceremony of the LGBTIQ community centre, which was attended by foreign missions and diplomats in Ghana. They contrast this with the statements from traditional leaders and religious leaders that renounces LGBTIQ persons and activities. It creates an impression of a

⁸ Human Rights Watch ‘Ghana: LGBT Activists Face Hardships After Detention; Extreme Anti-LGBT Bill Stokes Hostility’ (20 September 2021) <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/09/20/ghana-lgbt-activists-face-hardships-after-detention> (accessed 21 September 2021).

⁹ As above 13.

¹⁰ Amofo Akoto Robert ‘Ghana’s Legal and Policy Frameworks and the Protection of the Human Rights of LGBT People in Ghana’ (2018) Policy Brief page 1.

¹¹ Article 106 (2) Constitution of Ghana.

western agenda to promote LGBTIQ which is being rejected by the various leaders based on religious, cultural and traditional values. Contrary to this reasoning, there is evidence to the fact that LGBTIQ persons or same sex-sexual relations is not a Western import. Nana Agyemang, a human rights lawyer, has intimated through research that the first-ever study of homosexuality in Ghana in the 1950s, established that “men who have sex with men” were an integral, but obscured, part of Ghanaian culture and sexual relations.¹² From the Ghana Men’s Study by the Ghana AIDS Commission, there are same-sex loving people (men who have sex with other men) in Ghana who have never come across a western person or ever been to an urban area but have identified as persons who have same-sex sexual relations. The reasoning therefore that LGBTIQ issues are not Ghanaian is false and therefore not enough reason to base the making of a law that criminalises LGBTIQ persons in Ghana.

The majoritarian approach to this law is discriminatory

The sponsors of the bill also state in the Memorandum that there is an overwhelming consensus from multi-religious faiths and various traditional and customary custodians that reject the practice of and advocacy for the LGBTIQ groups based on customary law and tenets of faith and respect for public morality.

The question one could ask in this regard is if these religions, faiths and custodians of Ghanaian customs agree on every aspect of each other’s beliefs and practices. Christians believe that Jesus is the only way to God while Muslims believe that Mohammed is the final prophet and their direct messenger from God. Does this warrant the Christians, who are the majority in Ghana, the right to make laws to criminalise Islam because they do not follow Christian values and practices? Why are there no such laws but rather an attempt to ensure peaceful co-existence between Christians and Muslims?

Making a law based on the fact that a group of people agree on it and they are in the majority is therefore not enough grounds and has the potential to advance human rights abuse, discrimination and violence.

LGBTIQ activities do not threaten the existence of families

LGBTIQ persons have existed and do exist in families and that has not and is not destroying any family. The sponsors believe that the concept of the “Ghanaian family” is threatened which is a false assertion. The formation of Ghanaian families are not always based on a man and a woman as advanced in the Memorandum. There are unmarried aunties or uncles who form their own families by living with and taking care of the children of their siblings, cousins or neighbours who cannot afford to take care of their children. Well-to-do persons in Ghana are always encouraged to support other family members without basing the need for support on the sexual orientation or gender identity of the well-to-do person. Also, not all marriages that involve a male and a female end up in childbirth to form a family. Not all married heterosexual

¹² Nana Agyeman ‘Homosexuality isn’t alien to Ghanaian society’(17 March 2021) <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/beyond-trafficking-and-slavery/homosexuality-isnt-alien-ghanaian-society/> (accessed on 23 August 2021).

couples aim to form a family by reproducing therefore the formation of a family in Ghana is not based on only heterosexual couples coming together to give birth to make a family. Ghanaians have many different ways of calling others their family members or making people family.

Men Who have Sex with Men are not the highest mode of transmission of HIV; it is heterosexual sex

Sponsors of the Bill in the Memorandum on page 5 mention that the passage of the Bill is apt because of HIV prevalence among MSMs. They make an uneducated assertion which they allude to a non-existing entity “Science Research Council”. This is either an attempt to misinform or an attempt to take statistic and use it to wrongfully advance an assertion.

According to the Mode of Transmission Study Ghana, Heterosexual sex is the commonest mode of transmission of HIV in Ghana contributing to 72% of new infections in Ghana. This is followed by sex work that contributes 18% before MSM and Persons Who Inject Drugs contributing 9%.¹³ It is important to mention that the HIV infection among Sex Workers, MSM and PWIDs is heavily influenced by laws that criminalise their existence (for gay men and bisexual men) or their practice (for Sex Workers and PWIDs).

Basing the reasoning for proposing a law to criminalise same-sex activities based on 18.1% of individuals living with HIV is not fair, inferring from the statistics on the different groups. It will rather be expected that more effort is placed on funding, support and decriminalisation of Key Populations as recommended by UNAIDS, Global Funds, PEPFAR, who are the biggest donors to HIV programming in Ghana.

Impact of the Bill

1. Increase human rights abuse of LGBTIQ persons

LGBTIQ persons already face violence and human rights abuse based on their real or imputed sexual orientation and gender identity.¹⁴ The existing section 104 of Criminal Offences Act that criminalised unnatural carnal knowledge already contributes to hate crime and human rights abuse LGBTIQ persons face.¹⁵ The passage of the Bill into law will therefore further cement the human rights abuse that LGBTIQ persons are already facing. It will legitimise and support the perpetuation of crime against LGBTIQ persons in Ghana.

Most of the provisions in the Bill violate the constitutional rights of LGBTIQ persons and their inherent dignity as human beings and threaten their lives. Section 6 (e) of the Bill, for instance,

¹³ Ghana AIDS Commission ‘National HIV and AIDS Strategic Plan 2016-2020’(2016) page 23
<https://www.ghanaisds.gov.gh/mcadmin/Uploads/NSP%20Final%202016%20-%202020.pdf> (24 September 2021).

¹⁴ Solace Initiative and Alliance for Equality and Diversity ‘Understanding the Issues and Experiences of LGBT+ Ghanaians; A Baseline Study on Violence, Human Rights Abuses, Stigma, and Discrimination faced by the LGBT+ Community in Ghana’ (2019) page 15.

¹⁵ As above 6.

prohibits LGBTIQ persons from holding themselves out in their sexual orientation or gender identity. This is contrary to Article 21 (1) (a) and (b) which grants the right to all Ghanaians the freedom of speech and expression. The argument of restricting the rights of LGBTIQ persons because it is perceived as “injurious to public safety” is not supported with facts and figures to warrant the criminalisation of LGBTIQ persons. Sexual activity of any group –both heterosexuals and homosexuals - are not expected to be done in public. Criminalising LGBTIQ persons, their sexual activity or advocacy is an unreasonable restriction of the rights of these persons that does not stand the test for restricting of these rights.

In restricting the rights of any group of people it is important that the following questions¹⁶ are answered:

Is the restriction necessary?

Human rights can only be restricted to achieve an important and legitimate purpose. Decisions to restrict people’s rights should be based on evidence that the restriction is needed to achieve that purpose. The restriction of the constitutional rights of LGBTIQ persons in this bill will not achieve any legitimate aim as most of the basis stated for this bill is unfounded and based on myths, misconceptions and concepts that cannot be proven in law or research. It will rather further contribute to the human rights abuse of LGBTIQ persons. It is therefore not necessary to pass such a bill.

Sexual activity of gays, lesbians and bisexuals do not in any way cause any harm to others if done in private, with consent from a person who has the capacity to provide consent. There has been no substantive argument in the bill or its memorandum that is able to give specific harm or instances whereby same-sex loving people engaging in a sexual activity affect anyone negatively, which should warrant a law that will criminalise LGBTIQ persons.

Is the restriction proportionate?

Measures that restrict human rights should be the least restrictive possible. The means used to enforce these measures (such as fines and ‘move on’ powers) must be proportionate to their purpose. They must also have avenues for review or appeal. The current proposed bill requires a restriction on the rights of LGBTIQ persons (section 6(e)), persons who may engage them or know their sexual or gender identity and do not report (section 6 (f) section 12 (2) and (3)), restrict the media as against Article 21 (a) (section 12 (1) (a) and many others. They are charged with 5 and 10 years prison terms, which are unnecessary as they already infringe on the rights of these persons.

Does the restriction comply with existing laws, including discrimination laws?

¹⁶ Queensland Human Rights Commission ‘Limiting human rights: when can law and policy restrict rights?’(2020) Factsheet page 1
https://www.qhrc.qld.gov.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0006/26466/QHRC_factsheet_HRA_COVID19andlimitingrights.pdf

Article 17 (1) of the Constitution requires that all “All persons” be treated equal before the law. The current bill proposes the restriction of the rights of LGBTIQ persons because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. The Ghanaian Constitution requires in Article 12 (1) that all arms of government and all other government organs and agencies to respect the fundamental human rights and freedoms enshrined in the constitution. Making a law to restrict peoples’ rights when their existence and what they do does not disrespect the rights and freedoms of others and does not affect the public in any way is not in line with the law.

The Bill also goes against article 17 (2) forbids any form of discrimination. Making a law to deny people access to healthcare, human rights protection under the law, limiting their freedom of expression, conscience and belief, association and assembly because they are different from others is discriminatory and follows the principle of article 17 (2) of the constitution. This makes the bill not compliant with existing legal frameworks.

The passage of this Bill does not only go against human rights provisions in Ghana’s Constitution but also various international human rights treaties to which Ghana is a state party. One of such is the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights which requires state parties in Article 2 to ensure that “Every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognised and guaranteed in the present Charter without distinction of any kind such as race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth or other status.” The provision though does not mention sexual orientation and gender identity clearly states “everyone” and “other status”. It is also significant to mention Resolution 275¹⁷ (2014) of the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights (African Commission) where the African Commission condemns “the increasing incidence of violence and other human rights violations, including murder, rape, assault, arbitrary imprisonment and other forms of persecution of persons on the basis of their imputed or real sexual orientation or gender identity,”. It also calls on “State Parties to ensure that human rights defenders work in an enabling environment that is free of stigma, reprisals or criminal prosecution as a result of their human rights protection activities, including the rights of sexual minorities” and further requires “States to end all acts of violence and abuse, whether committed by State or non-state actors, including by enacting and effectively applying appropriate laws prohibiting and punishing all forms of violence including those targeting persons on the basis of their imputed or real sexual orientation or gender identity”.

Also, jurisprudence from UN treaty bodies, including General Comments, Concluding Observations, and Communications, have consistently and authoritatively indicated that international human rights conventions to which Ghana is party grant LGBT individuals equal rights and dignity.

¹⁷ African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights ‘275 Resolution on Protection against Violence and other Human Rights Violations against Persons on the basis of their real or imputed Sexual Orientation or Gender Identity’ - ACHPR/Res.275(LV)2014 Adopted at the 55th Ordinary Session of the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights in Luanda, Angola, 28 April to 12 May 2014
<https://www.achpr.org/sessions/resolutions?id=322> (accessed on 18 September 2021).

Is the restriction transparent?

The process of passing this Bill must be made transparent and open to ensure all persons are informed and participate actively. Due to the already vulnerable nature of LGBTIQ persons in Ghana, the active participation of LGBTIQ persons in the current process is questionable. Some parliamentarians have already made homophobic statements and have misinterpreted the existing law on unnatural carnal knowledge pitching it against LGBTIQ persons. This will make it difficult for parliament to engage LGBTIQ persons meaningfully to enable them to understand them and make their decision based on lived realities of these people.

To make the process transparent, Parliament needs to have a public hearing where they will invite LGBTIQ organisations, persons and Human Rights Organisations to make contributions to the process. They must create a conducive environment where LGBTIQ persons will not be threatened, harassed or intimidated when they decide to actively participate when they are called on.

Does the restriction protect the human worth and dignity of communities most at risk?

The current Bill contrary to the requirement of this principle rather creates an opportunity for abuse, harassment, violence and human rights abuse against LGBTIQ persons. The proposal to imprison people for 5 years because they only identified as Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Transexual Queer, Pansexual or Ally is rather punishing these groups of people for “holding themselves out,” when doing this does not harm any person or group of people.

Below are other human rights issues that could be as a result of the passage of the Bill into law if the current proposed provisions are maintained:

a. LGBTIQ persons could be denied access to service and Criminalises services providers

Section 12 (2)(a)(a) and (3) simply makes everyone who provides any service including healthcare, education, transportation, water, electricity or any other service to LGBTIQ persons a criminal and could face up to 10 years of imprisonment. For instance, if a person is known/suspected to be an LGBTIQ person he/she/they may be denied services by any service provider to ensure they (the service provider) is not arrested on suspicion of supporting persons criminalised under the act. Lawyers, doctors, architects, *trotro* drivers, taxi drivers and even food vendors are at risk of being prosecuted under this provision of the Bill. It will therefore make it difficult for any person who is suspected to be an LGBTIQ person access any service, even the most basic of them. This is inhumane, arbitrary, discriminatory and against local, international and regional human rights laws.

a. The bill increases discrimination against LGBT persons

As already stated above, the Bill places LGBTIQ persons in a position where they could be denied services because of their real or imputed sexual orientation or gender identity. It also places LGBTIQ people in a position where they will be discriminated against based on section

6 of the Bill. Section 6 (e) of the Bill identifies specifically LGBTTQPA and non-binary persons and prescribe a sanction for just identifying or calling oneself as any of these identities. Identifying minorities and making such a draconian law against them because of their sexual orientation or gender identity is discriminatory.

b. Affirms conversion therapy which negatively affects its victims

Section 20 prescribes various types of conversion therapy for LGBTIQ persons and “victims” of LGBTIQ activities. The UN Independent Expert on protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity has called for a global ban on conversion therapy. In his report, he defined conversion therapy as "interventions of a wide-ranging nature, all of which have in common the belief that a person's sexual orientation or gender identity can and should be changed. He identified that they inflict severe pain and suffering, which may in many circumstances amount to cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment or torture, resulting in long-lasting psychological and physical damage."¹⁸

Already, Ghana has a climate in which people are sexually, physically, emotionally and financially abused by medical doctors, spiritual/religious healers and self-styled prophets. This Bill will legitimize their practices as they can now identify a legal framework that allows them to use all means to convert people from one sexual orientation to heterosexuality. Again, these conversion therapy practices have never been proven as productive but rather cause emotional and psychological damage to people, who become suicidal or depressed.

c. Affect HIV programming by increasing HIV prevalence and reducing funding for HIV activities

Key populations as identified earlier suffer from the existing law that criminalises their existence and practices. The criminalisation of key populations is one of the main reasons for the rise in HIV prevalence among them.¹⁹ Due to the criminalisation of key populations, they fear persecution or discrimination against them when they try to access HIV prevention and treatment services. Health professionals who would like to provide these services can also face penalties for providing services for persons who are criminalised. This will contribute to increased HIV prevalence.

The majority of funding for HIV programming for key populations comes from donor funding. Section 14 (1) of the Bill prohibits donor funding for activities that supports LGBTIQ persons. Currently, gay men and bisexual men are all part of the MSMs in the key population umbrella that government agencies like Ghana AIDS Commission, National AIDS Control Programme and Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice receive funding from donor agencies to implement HIV programming. Criminalising funding for such activities will mean

¹⁸ Human Rights Council ‘Report of the Independent Expert on protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity; Practices of so-called “conversion therapy”’(2020) page 4 <https://daccess-ods.un.org/TMP/6283950.80566406.html> (accessed 27 September 2021).

¹⁹ Ghana AIDS Commission ‘National HIV and AIDS Strategic Plan 2016-2020’(2016) page 14 <https://www.ghanaims.gov.gh/mcadmin/Uploads/NSP%20Final%202016%20-%202020.pdf> (24 September 2021).

there will be no financing for HIV programming for MSMs which is likely to fuel the prevalence, not because of the sexual orientation of these people but because of this law that prevents them from accessing HIV services.

2. Closes civic spaces for the media and civil society and the general public

Ghana's civic space has been described as narrow on CIVICUS's Civic Space Monitor.²⁰ This Bill further exacerbates the situation by seeking to control the media and civil society on what they can and cannot telecast, especially of the LGBTIQ community.

Civic space is the bedrock of any open and democratic society. When civic space is open, citizens and civil society organisations are able to organise, participate and communicate without hindrance. In doing so, they are able to claim their rights and influence the political and social structures around them. This can only happen when a state holds by its duty to protect its citizens and respects and facilitates their fundamental rights to associate, assemble peacefully and freely express views and opinions.²¹

Section 12 (1) (a) and (b) limits the media on how and what they can express themselves, in relation to LGBTIQ issues. It also creates a situation where the media cannot play their role in seeking accountability and checking the government on this issue because they are not allowed in any way to say anything, most likely, positive about this issue. It limits their freedom of thought, conscience and belief as stated in Article 21 (1)(b). It also affects the general public who use social media and other platforms to express their views on issues. It closes the space to engage on this issue and shuts out the opportunity for accountability on the human rights protection of LGBTIQ persons. It also creates for internet providers and all forms of media, including social media, a strict liability on the content they host or publish that amounts to censorship.

First, section 13 (1)(a) and (b) is vague. It puts various groups including the media and academia in limbo on LGBTIQ issues. How will an academic who writes a paper on the need to protect LGBTIQ persons know that they are indirectly targeting children? How will a media person who expresses their freedom of conscience and belief be sure that at the time they are expressing themselves on the fact that LGBTIQ persons are normal individuals, a child will or will not be listening? How will one know that they have committed an offence by expressing themselves as they are entitled to?

This provision is not supported in law as it infringes on various rights of Ghanaians and takes away the opportunity for anyone to even seek a change of this law as civil society, the media and academia that advocate for change of laws will be gagged and could face the penalty prescribed if they make an attempt to do so. A society that does not create opportunities for

²⁰ CIVICUS 'Monitor; Tracking Civic Space: Ghana' (2021) <https://monitor.civicus.org/country/ghana/> (accessed 27 September 2021).

²¹ CIVICUS 'What is Civic Space'(2021) <https://monitor.civicus.org/whaticivicspace/> (accessed 28 September 2021).

dialogue on issues limits its people and control how they should think, believe and see issues. It does not facilitate progress, democracy and accountability on the side of government.

It is also worth mentioning that the Bill criminalise being an “ally” of LGBTIQ communities, therefore targeting all those mainstream human rights organizations and service providers, as well as state institutions such as the Ghana AIDS Commission (GAC) and the Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice (CHRAJ), that over time have voiced their support for human rights of LGBTIQ individuals and communities.

In September 2020, the United Nations Human Rights Committee, which interprets the ICCPR, adopted General Comment No. 37 on Article 21, the right of peaceful assembly urging countries to ensure that “laws and their interpretation and application do not result in discrimination in the enjoyment of the right of peaceful assembly for instance on the basis of sexual orientation or gender identity.” Any restrictions on peaceful assemblies “may not be imposed because of opposition to expressions of sexual orientation or gender identity.”

The Commission’s Resolution 376 on the Situation of Human Rights Defenders in Africa says that governments should adopt domestic legislation to protect human rights defenders working on issues related to sexual orientation and gender identity. The African Commission’s Guidelines for Policing Assemblies by Law Enforcement Officials in Africa also says that countries should train all law enforcement officials on the safety and protection of groups that may face limitations on their right to freedom of assembly, including on grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity.

3. Forced accusations that will increase insecurity

The Bill creates an opportunity for increased blackmail, scam and harassment of LGBTIQ persons. The Bill will be used as an instrument of leverage by unscrupulous individuals with homophobia to falsely accuse or harass LGBTIQ persons because they disagree with their sexual orientation. Section 6 (e) for instance can be used falsely against a person and because it is difficult to prove such an act, it may take a while to hold the accused person for investigations, which may later turn out to be false. Although the person who made the accusation could be punished, they may have caused irreparable damage to the person they accused and no compensation may be enough for the person to recover.

It will be unsafe for anyone to express themselves on such matters if their belief on the issue is contrary to what the Bill prescribes. It will limit conversations even in the privacy of people’s homes, offices and other places.

The police would have to continually deal with situations where they need to investigate such situations. They are already stretched with cases of violence, armed robbery, fraud and murders. Now, they have to also deal with the personal issues of sexual or gender identity, stressing state resources and inundating law enforcement with more work of policing people’s sexual identities. This may take them off critical issues that affect society directly and broadly

to dealing with who and how citizens are having consensual sex privately or how they identify themselves when they may not have engaged in any sexual activity.

4. Affect the poor and vulnerable more

Research shows that the poor are more likely to experience legal problems.²² Legal problems are often symptoms of poor policy, inadequate legal and institutional frameworks, and weak delivery of services. In 2018, the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights on his mission to Ghana identified that “Discrimination against lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex people makes them vulnerable to extreme poverty and living in poverty they experience intersecting forms of discrimination that prevent the full enjoyment of their human rights.”²³

Like many other already existing laws, poor and vulnerable people will bear the brunt of this Bill if passed into law. Since sexuality is usually a private activity, persons who are of a particular economic status who can afford a single tenancy home where they can have sexual intercourse with no intrusion will have a very limited chance of being affected by this law.

In Ghana, the majority of people live in shared compound homes where neighbours are likely to observe and monitor the activity of others. There is little to no full privacy which makes it likely that LGBTIQ persons could be reported as holding themselves out. Some of these accusations may be false, but as mentioned above, the falsely accused person may have already suffered some irreparable damages.

5. Ghana could lose its positive stance with some countries, inter-governmental organisations, international organisations and regional bodies

Ghana has positive credibility for its observation of democracy and human rights protection in Africa. Many of her relations with other nations, businesses and international organisations is based on Ghana’s image in this regard. Ghana’s record of being human rights compliant will be severely damaged if parliament passes a law that significantly infringes on the rights of vulnerable people.

At Ghana’s 3rd cycle for the Universal Periodic Review in 2017, Ghana supported some key recommendations that seek to protect LGBTIQ persons from violence and discrimination. Below are the recommendations²⁴:

²² Paul Prottitero ‘Poor People and the Law’ (6 December 2021) Brookings <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/future-development/2016/12/06/poor-people-and-the-law/> (accessed 28 September 2021).

²³ Human Rights Council ‘Report of the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights on his mission to Ghana’ A/HRC/38/33/Add.2 (2018) <https://undocs.org/A/HRC/38/33/Add.2> (accessed 27 September 2021).

²⁴ Human Rights Council ‘Thematic List of Recommendations’ *Ghana’s 3rd Cycle Universal Periodic Review 2017* pages 13-14 <https://www.ohchr.org/en/hrbodies/upr/pages/ghindex.aspx> (accessed 28 September 2021).

1. Take the steps necessary to protect lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex persons from violence and discrimination on the basis of their sexual orientation and gender identity (Ireland)
2. Take measures to fight against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity (Italy)
3. Eliminate the type of crime of “unnatural carnal knowledge” and adopt measures to eradicate discrimination motivated by sexual orientation and gender identity (Greece)

Having supported these recommendations at the Human Rights Council, Ghana is expected to take necessary steps to make these recommendations a reality. Passing the current Bill into law will contradict this position. Ghana is up for its 4th cycle review in 2023. At this review, Ghana will be expected to give an update or progress on these issues the country supported. Passing the Bill will mean that Ghana has retrogressed, instead of progressing in this regard. As already discussed, passing such a law rather increases human rights abuse, discrimination, violence and impunity.

Ghana also depends on its image as a peace-loving, people-centred country with a culture of tolerance, diversity, hospitality, freedom and justice. Many investors, international personalities and celebrities choose Ghana as a preferred location for various events and activities because of these positive and welcoming qualities. These attributes give Ghana more global visibility, attention and shores up her positive image that draws a lot of opportunities to the Ghanaian people. Passing the Bill will upset investor confidence, denigrate Ghana as an intolerant state and lose out on a lot of touristic opportunities for the nation and people as a whole.

Recommendations:

1. Withdraw the enactment of the Bill into law; Executive and Legislators have a responsibility to protect vulnerable people

The legislature and executive must reject this law and have it withdrawn. It is based on myths, misconceptions and misinterpretation of facts, issues and information as shown earlier. A law that is based on the beliefs, religion and prejudice of a group of people against the vulnerable who cause no harm to their existence does not need to be supported or allowed to be enacted.

Members of parliament have a responsibility to question and put Bills of this nature to strict proof and test since it seeks to specifically criminalise a group of people who are members of their constituencies and because of their situation may not be able to do this for themselves. MPs owe it to every member of their constituency to represent them equally. Putting personal religious and cultural beliefs ahead of human rights protection of a vulnerable group of people will perpetually increase human rights abuse, violence and discrimination against these people.

The Executive have a responsibility to ensure that the laws that are presented have “cabinet memorandums” that are legally and constitutionally sound. The Executive can ensure that the

Bill is tested against Article 107 (b) which prohibits the passage of any legislation which adversely affects the personal rights and liberties of any person or to impose a burden. This bill seriously affects the human rights of LGBTIQ persons in Ghana, putting a burden on the state and other persons unnecessarily.

2. Provide a platform for LGBT+ organisations and advocates

LGBTIQ organisations and advocates are in a vulnerable position at this time. Their work has been misconstrued and misrepresented by the memorandum to the Bill. Contrary to what the Bill suggests, many of the LGBTIQ organisations and advocates focus on advancing and protecting the human rights of sexual minorities, as enshrined in the constitution.

They provide critical and relevant support services that mainstream organisations do not provide because of the sexual orientation or gender identity of people who are in the LGBTIQ community. They also ensure that LGBTIQ persons are protected from harm, discrimination and abuse from society. Ultimately, they fill a gap that government has no arrangement or system for. It will therefore be contradictory that a law is made to criminalise or as stated in sections 15 and 16 of the Bill, disband and prohibit the critical service these organisations and advocates provide. LGBTIQ organisations and advocates must therefore be given a platform to be able to meaningfully engage the government and show the work they do as well as receive the needed support to continue playing the role of supporting vulnerable people, especially LGBTIQ persons.

3. Enact laws to protect LGBT+ persons from violence and human rights abuse

LGBTIQ persons are vulnerable people who need protection and support from government institutions. In countries like South Africa, Mozambique, Angola and many Francophone African countries, LGBTIQ is decriminalised and some of these countries have gone ahead to enact laws that protect LGBTIQ persons from discrimination.

In Ghana, LGBTIQ persons face human rights abuse, discrimination and violence. They are not able to report these issues because of fear of being further persecuted by the police. Others are forced to flee from home, their communities and even the country. As persons whose existence does not cause harm or danger to anyone, putting in place such a bill will rather further endanger their lives because people who hate LGBTIQ persons will now have a tool to perpetuate their animosity.

Conclusion

The current Bill is premised on myths, misconceptions and misinformation and motivated by prejudice. Making a law to criminalise people on false accusations and misunderstanding of who a group of people are only furthering their suffering and give people who hate them an opportunity to continue abusing them. It is therefore important that all persons in the law-making process question the basis for enacting this law and ask critical questions on the constitutionality of this Bill as well as how it advances the development of Ghana.

Possible knock-on effects from the Bill include a predictable surge in citizen attacks, harassment, and blackmail of LGBTIQ persons or those perceived to belong to the LGBTIQ community. It is well documented that laws directed at criminalizing marginalized groups almost always lead to a spike in targeted violence against such groups. The Bill makes the LGBTIQ community vulnerable, exposing them to extreme and rampant discrimination and abuse.

It is morally reprehensible to legislate laws against consensual relationships between two adults, as such laws devalue our collective sense of human worth, respect, freedom and dignity. Homophobic laws do not represent, do not uplift African values or preserve family values. It rather estranges people from their families, communities and loved ones. It feels particularly bothersome, shameful even, that in a difficult time marked by the impact of a significant pandemic, there is a proposed Bill by lawmakers to make the lives of their people more miserable. The Bill will destroy lives, not build lives.

Ghana will be unsafe for many and the nation may lose not only some of its talented and valuable people but opportunities to advance in its democracy and human rights since this Bill draws back Ghana's image as a democratic and human rights compliant country.